

⚓ SWE25 Expedition report ⚓

1. Expedition Overview

- **Title of Expedition:** SWE25 expedition
- **Dates:** 01-08 July 2025 (mobilization on June 30th)
- **Duration:** 8 days
- **Vessel Name:** R/V Svea
- **Departure Port / Return Port:** Lysekil, Sweden
- **Cruise leader:** Eric Capo (Carina Bunse as alternate)

2. Purpose and Objectives

The main goal of this cruise is to collect new data from the water column and sediments of the Swedish West Coast. The **Biox project** will produce new data from the water column and sedimentary archives of five Swedish fjords (Gullmarn, Byfjorden, Havstensfjorden, Kosterfjord and Idefjorden) to characterise their biogeochemistry and resident microorganisms and how past and ongoing deoxygenation events have impacted these ecosystems. The **EcoAct project** will provide new knowledge about the ecology of marine actinomycetes and metabolite-mediated interactions using water, plankton nets and sediment samples collected from coastal and offshore stations at the Swedish West Coast.

Biox project: Exploring the biogeochemistry and microbial ecology of oxygen-depleted fjords: historical and modern insights.

- **PI(s):** Eric Capo (Umeå University), Stefan Bertilsson (SLU), Erik Björn (Umeå University), Stefano Bonaglia (Gothenburg University), Carina Bunse (University of Gothenburg), Jeffrey Hawkes (Uppsala University), Helena Filipsson (Lund Univ), Francisco Nascimento (Stockholm University), Courtney Stairs (Lund University)
- **Objectives:**
 - Aim 1 - Characterization of fjord pelagic and benthic redoxclines to provide the first biogeochemical map of Swedish fjords
 - Aim 2 Multi-omics investigation of microbial communities occupying oxygen-depleted fjord systems to identify abundant and keystone species for ecosystem function.

- Aim 3 Fjords history reconstruction from the sediment record to inform on the effects of past environmental changes on biotic communities.

EcoAct: Ecophysiology of marine Actinomycetes

- **PI(s):** Carina Bunse (University of Gothenburg)
- **Objectives:**
 - Aim1 - Study microbial biodiversity (phytoplankton and universal 16S/18S rRNA amplicons) in the pelagic and surface sediment layer (sinking POM)
 - Aim2 - In-depth environmental studies of marine Actinomycetes
 - Aim3 - Measure ecophysiological rates in microcosm incubations along temperature and DOM gradients
 - Aim4 - Identify metabolite-mediated interactions between marine microorganisms at the Swedish West Coast and by challenging model microbes with a variety of environmental microorganisms

3. Study Area

- **Location:** For the Biox project, the sites sampled were 5 fjords along the Swedish West Coast (Gullmarn, Byfjorden, Havstensfjorden, Kosterfjord and Idefjorden). For the EcoAct project, two transects (nearshore and offshore) were taken along the coast. Sites were shared between the two projects to study the connectivity of microbial communities between the fjord systems.

- **Map:** Map of sampled stations

Station List: Table with Station ID, Coordinates, Depth, Project

Station_id	CTD Lat Lon	Water depth	Project
SWE25-01 (Byfjorden)	58°20.1032' N, 11°52.7868' E	46m	Biox
SWE25-02 (Hasvtenfjorden)	58°18.7135' N, 11°46.2474' E	40m	Biox

SWE25-03 (Gullmarn)	58°19.2860' N, 11°32.6830' E	18m	Biox
SWE25-04	58°15.3049' N, 11°14.6074' E	53m	EcoAct/Biox
SWE25-06	58°29.0354' N, 11°8.7585' E	54m	EcoAct
SWE25-08	58°40.9742' N, 11°4.8436' E	62m	EcoAct
SWE25-10	58°50.5036' N, 11°6.0717' E	224m	EcoAct
SWE25-12 (Kosterfjord)	58°54.6693' N, 11°3.948' E	200m	Biox
SWE25-14	58°57.9992' N, 11°3.4318' E	206m	EcoAct
SWE25-16	59°6.447' N, 11°18.4734' E	?	Biox
SWE25-18	59°4.7790' N, 11°22.9130' E	36m	Biox
SWE25-19 (Idefjorden)	59°3.0472' N, 11°24.3995' E	36m	Biox
SWE25-20	58°56.6306' N, 10°58.1325' E	37m	EcoAct
SWE25-21	58°54.6013' N, 10°55.5528' E	30m	EcoAct
SWE25-23	58°49.8122' N, 10°56.9454' E	50m	EcoAct
SWE25-25	?	49m	EcoAct
SWE25-27	58°30.9201' N, 10°59.8837' E	58m	EcoAct
SWE25-28	58°26.9625' N, 10°59.9232' E	?	EcoAct
SWE25-29	58°21.1993' N, 10°59.8138' E	?	EcoAct
SWE25-30	58°14.8023' N, 11°4.3722' E	?	EcoAct

4. Sampling Plan

12h shift - First CTD 8 am, end of the last CTD 8 pm

Rosette for water sampling is 24 bottles of 5 L

For Biox fjord stations - Gullarm (station 3, GUL), Byfjorden (station 1, BYF), Havstenfjorden (station 2, HAV), Kosterfjorden (station 12, KOS), Idefjorden (station 18 IDE) and 3 depths in the stations - 6-8 water depths were sampled. Measured parameters are CTD, biogeochemical parameters, DNA, RNA, single-cell, plankton,

ecophysiology assays, DOM, experiments, dissolved & particulate nutrients. Sediment will be collected with GEMAX for the 5 fjord stations and with a 6m gravity corer for station 3 (Gullmarn)

For **EcoAct stations** (4-14, 20-30) & **Biox connecting stations** (4,7 and 14-17, 19), 3-5 water depths were sampled. Measured parameters are CTD, DNA (amplicons/metagenomics), plankton, ecophysiology assays, DOM, co-culture experiments, dissolved & particulate nutrients, pigments. Sediment for microbial isolation will be collected with a box corer or other corers available.

Methods used

- A CTD-Rosette 24 bottles of 5 L was used to collect water in all stations.
- The CTD was operated by Örjan Bäck (SMHI).
- CTD data included pressure (db), depth (m), temperature (C), salinity (psu), density (kg/m³), dissolved oxygen concentration (ml/L), dissolved oxygen saturation (%), fluorescence (mg/m³), turbidity (NTU), PAR (uE/m²sec)
- A ferry box was used to collect data from 6 m (chlorophyll, temp, salinity, pCO₂).
- A short video was recorded by the CTD to visualize sediment bottom.
- Nets were used to collect phytoplankton (10 µm, 0-20 m) and zooplankton (90 µm, 0-25 m) in all stations.
- A secchi disk was used for water transparency
- A GEMAX corer was used to collect sediment short cores at stations SWE25_03, SWE25_01, SWE25_02, SWE25_12, SWE25_16 and SWE25_19.
- A 6 m gravity corer was used to collect a long-core at station SWE25_01. The core was collected by Svea crew with help from Ursula Schwarz and Helena Filippson. Ursula Schwarz and Helena Filippson sectioned the cores into 5 1m cores (I, II, III, IV, V, VI), the upper 1 m being not usable. Ursula Schwarz did longitudinal sectioning.

Overview of the water sampling strategy

Data	Sampling/Handling	Storage onboard	Analysis	Funds	Sharing
Rosette/CTD (24 bottles of 5 L)	Cast (Örjan)	na	na	Capo/Bunse	all
<i>Directly from the tap</i>					
STOX, H2S	Data (Meifang/Marta)	na	onboard	Capo	all
GHG, DIC	100 mL from each bottle (Tobia)	4°C	Bonaglia lab	Bonaglia	Bonaglia
Trace elements (TE, REE)	150 mL for filtration w/ 0.2 µm syringe filter; directly from tap (Teresa)	RT, pH2	Oldenburg lab	Bunse	Bunse
Nutrients	150 mL for filtration with 0.2 µm syringe filter; directly from tap (Teresa)	-20°C	Kristineberg	Capo	all
Fe	2 mL fixed in HCl (final conc. 0.5M), water directly from the tap from each niskin (Júlia)	4°C	ICM	Capo	all
AVS (H2S)	2 mL fixed in Zinc Acetate (final conc. 5% ZnAc) from each niskin (Júlia)	-20°C	Björn lab/ICM	Capo	all
TOC/TN	80 mL collected directly from the tap from each niskin (Júlia)	4°C	Björn lab/ICM	Capo	all
MeHg	300 mL collected directly from the tap from each niskin	4 °C	Björn lab/ICM	Björn	Björn
MMHg	300 mL collected directly from the tap from each niskin	4 °C	Björn lab/ICM	Björn	Björn
THg	120 mL collected directly from the tap from each niskin	4 °C	Björn lab/ICM	Björn	Björn
CDOM/FDOM	80 mL directly from the tap w/ teflon filtration unit (GFF) from each niskin (Júlia/Isa)	4 °C	Björn lab/ICM	Björn	all
Unfiltered Hg samples for incubations	1.2 L collected in the glove bag from one niskin each depth (Isa)	4 °C	Björn lab/ICM	Björn	Björn
<i>Rinse 19 L container and collect remaining water into a 19 L container (Meifang)</i>					
<i>A. Filter 6 L with 200 µm mesh into a new container (Meifang)</i>					
3 µm filters for amplicon/metaG	Filter 1 L x 3 with and place into 2 mL tube (Meifang)	-20C	Stairs lab	Capo/Stairs/Bertilsson	See section 7
3 µm filters for metatranscriptomics	Filter 1 L x 3 with and place into 2 mL tube (Meifang)	RNAlater -20C	Stairs lab	Capo/Stairs/Bertilsson	See section 7
0.2 µm filter for metaG/amplicon	Filter 1 L x 3 with 0.2 µm stx and place into 2 mL tube (Meifang)	-20C	Capo lab	Capo/Stairs/Bertilsson	See section 7
0.2 µm filter for metatranscriptomics	Filter 1 L x 3 with 0.2 µm stx (Meifang)	RNAlater and -20C	Capo lab	Capo/Stairs/Bertilsson	See section 7
Viral omics	Concentrate 1-5 L to 10	Time	Stairs lab	Stairs	Stairs

	mL using 100 kDa MWCO concentrated water (Sofia)	consuming			
DOM spec analysis	Acidify 1-5 L of 0.2 um filtered water (Meifang)	Room temperature	Hawkes lab	Hawkes	Hawkes
<i>B. From unfiltered water</i>					
3 liter 0.2 um filter for amplicon	Filter 1 L x 3 with 0.2 um stx and place into ziplock bag (Nicolai/Carina)	-20C	Bunse lab/SciLife Lab	Bunse	Bunse
Ecophysiology	150 mL for on-board incubations (Nicolai) only surface & DCM	-80	Bunse lab	Bunse	Bunse
Bacteria counts (FC)	25 ml (Nicolai)	-80	Bunse lab	Bunse	Bunse
Phytoplankton	125 mL (Olga)	Acidic Lugol, RT	Bunse	Bunse	all
Single-cell	10 mL fixed into glycerol (Stefan)	-80C	Bertilsson lab	Bertilsson	?
Pathogen cultivation	10 mL for cultivation (Stefan)	Room temp	Bertilsson lab	Bertilsson	Bertilsson
Microbial Isolation	1-2L for filtering and fixing sample in Glutaraldehyde (Sofia & Nik)	na	Stairs lab	Stairs	Stairs

Overview of the sediment sampling strategy

Data	Sampling/Handling	Stored	Analysis	Funds	Sharing
Foraminifera/CTG label (Fangting)	Core A - Subsample (0.5-3 cm) in tubes	?	Filipsson lab	Filipsson	Filipsson
Pb210 dating (Corentin)	Core B - Subsample into 15 mL falcon tubes	RT	To outsource	Capo	all
Geochemistry XRF (Fangting)	Core C - Subsample in 15 mL Falcon tubes	RT	To Umeå	Capo	all
sedDNA (Corentin)	Core D - Subsample into 50 mL falcon tubes	-20C	Capo lab	Capo	all
GHG (Tobia)	Core E - Subsampling GHGs in porewater of 20-30 cm sediment core, place sediment (3 mL) in glass vials, preserved with ZnCl ₂	+4C	Bonaglia lab	Bonaglia	Bonaglia
PAEs/PFAs (Elise)	Core F - subsampling of 3 layers (0-2 cm, 2-5, 5-10), place them in tubes.	-20C	Bonaglia lab	Bonaglia	Bonaglia
Ecophysiology (Carina)	Core G - Collect surface sediments	na	Bunse lab	Bunse	Bunse
Microbial isolation (Courtney)	Core H - Collect in the top 10 cm	Room temp	Stairs lab	Stairs	Stairs
Pathogen culture (Corentin)	Core G/H - Collect surface sediments		Bertilsson lab	Bertilsson	Bertilsson
Metazoans (Tobia)	Core G/H - Collect surface sediments		Nascimento lab	Nascimento	Nascimento

Plan for 6m gravity corer sediment sampling for station 3 - Biox

Data	Sampling/Handling	Stored	Analyses	Funds	Sharing
sedDNA (Corentin)	Subsample into 50 mL falcon tubes	-20C	Capo lab	Capo	all
Pb210 (Fangting)	Subsample into 15 mL falcon	RT	To Umeå	Capo	all
GeoX/XRF (Fangting)	Subsample in 15 mL falcon	RT	To Umeå	Capo	all
Foraminifera (Fangting)	Subsamples (0.5-3 cm)	?	Filipsson lab	Filipsson	Filipsson
C14	?	?	?	?	?

Metadata obtained during the cruise.

The SWE25 route and metadata were collected by Mats Wallin (SLU) using the software Olex and Svepa.

For each station, data obtained is described below.

Station SWE25_03 (Gullmarn)

Project	SWE25
Date	250701
Station_id	SWE25_03
Station_coordinates	58°19.2860' N, 11°32.6830' E
Weather	sunny
Water depth	about 118 m
Arrival time	08:30
#CTD Casts	2

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Cast_id	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Water depth (m)	118	100	80	60	50	40	19.5	6	65	60	55	30	19.5	6	2
Bottles_id	1-2-2003	4-5-2006	7-8-2009	10-11-12	13-14-15	16-17-18	19-20-21	22-23-24	1-2-2003	4-5-2006	7-8-2009	10-11-12	13-14-15	16-17-18	19-20-21
CTD Conductivity	na														
CTD Temp (°C)	na														
CTD O2 (µM)	na														
CTD fluorescence	na														
STOX O2 (µM)	158.54	160.5	162.8	no	202.5	185	217.7	225.4	203.1	182.4	176.4	202.1	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	13.09	13.1	13.11	no	13.12	13.14	13.15	13.16	16	16.03	16.04	16.05	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	-1.59	4.47	-0.67	no	1.02	-1-15	0.52	0.4	-1.24	-0.78	-0.6	-0.13	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	13.05	13.05	13.02	no	13	12.59	12.58	12.56	16.12	16.11	16.1	16.09	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na	no	na										
Comments (e.g. water smell)	no smell	no smell	no smell	no	no smell										
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes	no	yes										
Júlias Hg incubation	no														
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	yes	no													
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	no	no	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	yes	no													
Jeffs DOM mass spec	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no						

Stefans single cell and pathogen	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Teresas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	no	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N	N,TE	N	N	N	N	N
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Carinas MG	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Categories for Carina							DCM	surface							

Figure 1 - Ancillary data from the CTD Cast1 and Cast2.

Figure 2 - CTD camera photo of bottom sediments

GEMAX sediment sampling

Start time for Gemax coring: 3.09 pm

GEMAX cast	GEMAX core	Data type	Comments
1	A	pfas	58 cm
1	B		56.5 cm
2	C	core tops (0 - 2 cm)	52 cm
2	D		51.5 cm
3	E	Tobia	?
3	F	dating 210pb	59 cm
4	G	forams/XRF-TOC	58 cm
4	H	sedDNA	60 cm

Sediment core description - Structure dominated by fine silty clay. Core colored of dark grey clay to brown silty clay. Core G: forams/XRF-TOC. Due to limitation of the sectioning instrument, we were only able to collect the sediment up to depth 37 cm (36 – 37cm was the last layer). Presence of bubbles that moved from the bottom to

the surface layer of the sediment core. Bioturbation of the whole core. Presence of shell fragments. Core F: dating. Tobia and Elise sectioned it to 40 cm. Core C: core tops. 0 – 0.5 cm; 0.5 – 1 cm: 2 turn instead of 1.5; 1 – 1.5 cm; 1.5 – 2 cm.

Gravity corer sediment sampling

Samples were taken for foraminifera, geochemistry, sedDNA. Half of sediment cores have been kept 4 C for archives. sedDNA samples have been stored at -20C, other samples at 4C (Svea garbage room).

Sediment core description - **Core I** dominated by fine silty clay absence of odor well oxygenated may be already mineralized: 98-100; 90-92; 82-84; 74-76; 66-68; 58-60 black dark grey; 50-52 black dark grey; 42-44 becoming sticky; 34-36; 26-28; 18-20; 10-12; 2-4 - **Core II**: 98-100; 90-92; 82-84; 74-76; 66-68 shell fragment; 58-60 black dark grey high toc content may; 50-52 black dark grey; 42-44 shell fragment; 34-36; 26-28; 18-20 black dark grey; 10-12 black dark grey; 2-4 black dark grey - **Core III**: 98-100; 90-92 black dark grey; 82-84; 79.5-80.5 lamination; 74-76 black; 66-68 black; 56.5-58.5 lamination coarser sandy; 58-60; 50-52; 42-44; 34-36; 26-28; 18-20; 10-12 disturbed; 2-4 - **Core IV**: 98-100; 90-92; 82-84; 74-76; 64-66 big shell; 62-66.5 c dating; 58-60 big shell; 50-52; 42-44 becoming s; 34-36; 26-28; 18-20; 10-12; 2-4 - **Core V**: The top section of the core is disturbed; 98-100; 90-92 black; 82-84; 74-76 black dark; 66-68; 58-60; 50-52; 42-44; 34-36; 26-28; 18-20 shells; 1-4

CDOM-FDOM)																		
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes								
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes								
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes								
Stefans single cell and pathogen	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes								
Terasas N,TE	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N,TE								
Carinas amplicon	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes								
Carinas MG	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	no	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes								
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	no	yes
Categories for Carina					DCM			surface						DCM				surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

GEMAX sediment sampling

GEMAX cast	GEMAX core	Data type	Comments
1	A	sedDNA	68 cm
1	B	Dating 210 pb	69 cm
2	C	core tops (0 - 2 cm)	56 cm
3	D	Tobia	
4	E	forams/XRF-TOC	70 cm
5	F		37 cm

6
6

G
H

pfas

69 cm
70 cm

Sediment core description - Black color: high organic content and likely reduced chemical condition (probably hypoxia/anoxia). Earthy smell. Top section very fluffy and unconsolidated. Surface layer less reliable. Presence of worm and centipede like animals in the surface layer. Core A: sedDNA; Brownish dark top; Top 4 – 5 cm: quite watery and going into darker color; Up to 30 cm: deep black color with H₂S smell. Presence of some lighter grey color layer; Consistence going from watery to “creamier” and then up to LB media with low agar agar concentration. Core B: dating 210 pb; 16 – 17 cm coarser.

Station SWE25_02 (Havstensfjorden)

Project	SWE25
Date	250702
Station_id	SWE25_02
Station_coordinates	58°18.7135' N, 11°46.2474' E
Weather	cloudy
Water depth	about 40 m
Arrival time	13:15

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
Cast_id	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Water depth (m)	35	33	25	18	15	14	10	6	2	40	30	20	19	17	15	13	6

Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	yes
Categories for Carina					DC M			surf fac e							DC M			surf fac e

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

GEMAX sediment sampling

GEMAX cast	GEMAX core	Data type	Comments
1	A		42 cm
2	B	pfas	52.5 cm
2	C	Dating 210 pb	55 cm
3	D		52.5 cm
3	E	Tobia	53 cm
4	F	core tops	54 cm
5	G	sedDNA	54.5 cm
5	H	Forams/XRF-TOC	52 cm

Sediment core description - Black, high organic content. Consistency a bit granular, not really homogeneous. Less smelly than station 1. sedDNA samples found outside the freezer at 09:00 am the 04.07.2025, 36 hours after their sampling. We don't know if they never were put (Corentin could not go in the water lab because of contamination risk so someone else was tasked of doing it). Either out for 36 hours or removed sometimes in end of day 03.07.2025 and left out for 12 hours. Still usable?

Station SWE25_04

Project	SWE25
Date	250703
Station_id	SWE25_04
Station_coordinates	58°15.3049' N, 11°14.6074' E
Weather	Sunny, slight wind
Water depth	about 53 m
Arrival time	08:00

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4
Cast_id	1	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	52	33	20	6
Bottles_id	1-5	6-10	11-15	16-20
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	yes	no	no	yes
Terasas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes	yes

Carinas POM, pigments	no	yes	no	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	yes	no	yes
Categories for Carina		DCM		surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

Station SWE25_06

Project	SWE25
Date	250703
Station_id	SWE25_06
Station_coordinates	58°29.0354' N, 11°8.7585' E
Weather	Sunny
Water depth	about 54 m

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4
Cast_id	1	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	53	35	15	6
Bottles_id	1-5	6-10	11-15	16-20
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	yes	no	no	yes
Terasas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	yes	yes

Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	yes	yes
Categories for Carina			DCM	surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

Station SWE25_08

Project	SWE25
Date	250703
Station_id	SWE25_08
Station_coordinates	58°40.9742' N, 11°4.8436' E
Weather	Sunny
Water depth	about 62 m
Arrival time	

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4
Cast_id	1	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	62	35	15	6
Bottles_id	1-5	6-10	11-15	16-20
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	yes	no	no	yes
Terasas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes	yes

Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	yes	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	yes	yes
Categories for Carina			DCM	surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

Station SWE25_10

Project	SWE25
Date	250704
Station_id	SWE25_10
Station_coordinates	58°50.5036' N, 11°6.0717' E
Weather	Sunny
Water depth	about 224 m
Arrival time	08:00

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4	5
Cast_id	1	1	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	224	150	50	14	6
Bottles_id	1-5	6-10	11-15	16-20	21-24
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	no	no	no	no	no
Terasas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes

Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	no	yes	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	no	yes	yes
Categories for Carina				DCM	surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

CDOM-FDOM)																		
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	yes														
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no	yes													
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	yes														
Stefans single cell and pathogen	no	no	no	yes														
Terasas N,TE	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N,TE								
Carinas amplicon	no	no	no	yes														
Carinas MG	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no						
Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Carinas Flow Cytometry	no	no	no	yes														
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na						
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Categories for Carina							DC M	surfac e							DCM			surfac e

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

GEMAX sediment sampling

GEMAX cast	GEMAX core	Data type	Comments
1	A	pfas	37.5 cm
1	B		38 cm
2	C	Tobia	41.5 cm
2	D	core tops	41.5 cm
3	E	Forams/XRF-TOC	46.5 cm
3	F	Dating 210 pb	44 cm
4	G	sedDNA	42 cm
4	H		40 cm

Sediment core description - Color of the core was dark grey and becoming darker with depth up to deep black. Core E: forams. Presence of worms in the core (bioturbation). Sectioning up to 37 cm; Core F: dating 210 pb. The first cm was tilted. The sectioning was up to 31 cm depth with the presence of a sandy bottom. Presence of bioturbation; Core G: sedDNA. First 5 cm were tilted and therefore not fully complete (no perfect circle). Description of the core can be expanded to the other one (aside from bioturbation). From 6 – 7 cm on: very dense consistence. From 10 cm one: ice cream texture, quite solid. From 15 cm: H₂S smell consistent but going up and down with depth (decreasing at 17 cm and increasing a lot at 22 cm). 24 – 25 cm: presence of shells. Presence of a spatial heterogeneity in the core as presence of tunnels in the core. When sediment black, not around these tunnels that were grey (oxygenation of the deep sediment through the tunnel?).

Station SWE25_14

Project	SWE25
Date	250704
Station_id	SWE25_14
Station_coordinates	58°57.9992' N, 11°3.4318' E
Weather	Cloudy/rainy
Water depth	about 206 m
Arrival time	

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4	5
Cast_id	1	1	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	206	150	50	10	6
Bottles_id	1-5	6-10	11-15	16-20	21-24
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	no	no	no	no	no
Terasas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes

Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	no	yes	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	no	yes	yes
Categories for Carina				surface	surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

Station SWE25_16

Project	SWE25
Date	250705
Station_id	SWE25_16
Station_coordinates	59°6.447' N, 11°18.4734' E
Weather	foggy
Water depth	about 200 m
Arrival time	10h30

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Cast_id	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	38	35	21	18	16	15	13	10	6	2
Bottles_id	1-2	3-5	6-7	8-9	10-11	12-13	14-15	16-18	19-22	23-24
CTD Conductivity	na									
CTD Temp (°C)	na									
CTD O2 (µM)	na									
CTD fluorescence	na									
STOX O2 (µM)	127.43	101.09	94.53	91.27	104.05	116.29	151.89	142.3	194.42	245.95
STOX O2 sampling time	09:10	09:25	09:24	09:23	09:22	09:20	09:19	09:14	09:13	09:12
US H2S (µM)	-1.81	-1.29	-1.72	-1.6	-1.57	-1.24	-1.47	-1.35	-1.25	-0.93
H2S sampling time	09:28	09:30	09:31	09:32	09:34	09:35	09:36	09:37	09:39	09:40
Water color	na									
Comments (e.g, water smell)	no smell									
Tobias GHG DIC	yes									
Júlias Hg incubation	no									
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no
Courtneys viral analysis	yes									
Stefans single cell and pathogen	yes									
Terasas N,TE	N	N,TE	N,TE	N	N	N	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N
Carinas amplicon	no	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no
Carinas MG	no									
Carinas POM, pigments	no	yes	yes	no						

Carinas Flow Cytometry	no	yes	yes	no	no	no	yes	yes	yes	no
Carinas Actinos	na	na								
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	yes	yes	no						
Categories for Carina								DCM	surface	
Meifangs extra DNA	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

GEMAX sediment sampling

GEMAX cast	GEMAX core	Data type	Comments
1	A	core tops	29 cm
2	B		53 cm
2	C	Tobia	46 cm
3	D	Forams/XRF-TOC	51 cm
3	E	Dating 210 pb	56 cm
4	F	Pfas - mercury	52 cm
4	G	sedDNA	50 cm

Sediment core description - The top layer was really watery. Surface layer light grey (oxic) and getting darker with depth up to completely black (anoxia or hypoxia). A strong H₂S smell was present with the black color but at 31 cm depth (for core G) and on, no smell and color getting light grey again (oxic). Consistency was also a bit granular and very sticky. A bit redundant with sediment core description but more detailed in the depth. **Core G**: sedDNA. Bubbles released from the bottom sediment core when put on the slicer and went through all the sediment core up to the surface. Only on one side of the core, that disturbed it, so we did not sample this side (at the best of our capabilities). 8 cm: full black no smell. 15 cm to 31 cm: full black with strong H₂S smell. From 31 cm on: sulfide smell disappear and color become light grey again.

Cast 3 D Cast 3 E

Cast 4 G Cast 4 F

Cast 1 ?

CDOM-FDOM)																	
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes							
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	no	no	yes
Stefans single cell and pathogen	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	no	no	yes
Terasas N,TE	N	no	no	N	N	no	no	no	N	N,TE							
Carinas amplicon	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes							
Carinas MG	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes							
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes
Categories for Carina					DCM												surface
Meifangs extra DNA	yes	no	yes	no													

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

GEMAX sediment sampling

GEMAX cast

GEMAX core

Data type

Comments

1	A	Tobia	
1	B		58 cm
2	C	pfas	55 cm
2	D		55 cm
3	E	sedDNA	57 cm
3	F	core tops	56 cm
4	G	Dating 210 pb	58 cm
4	H	Forams/XRF-TOC	57 cm

Sediment core description - Sediment core was deep black directly from the top (anoxia/hypoxia). The top first cm presenting a mix of black and some clear brown strips. The sediment core consistence was quite particulates, not mixing well with water. The bottom of the core was light grey, meaning oxic, with a clay like consistency. Core F: core tops. Bubbles disturbing the core. Core G: dating 210 pb. Bubbles disturbing the core. From 20 cm deep, become oxic. 20 – 30 cm: very oxic. Core E: sedDNA. 18 – 20 cm: presence of a rock/residue of melted metal in the core that disturbed the sub sampling. All top layer anoxic. From 16 cm: mix light grey and deep black sediment (mix oxic – anoxic?)- From 25 cm on: fully oxic with light grey color only. No H2S smell through the all column, even in the deep black sediment.

Cast 2 D Cast 1 B
Cast 2 C

Cast 3 F Cast 3 E

Cast 4 H Cast 4 G

Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes						
Carinas Actinos	na	na						
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
Categories for Carina							surface	DCM
Meifangs extra DNA	no	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

None

Station SWE25_20

Project	SWE25
Date	250706
Station_id	SWE25_20
Station_coordinates	58°56.6306' N, 10°58.1325' E
Weather	Sunny, waves
Water depth	about 37 m
Arrival time	13:00

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4
Cast_id	1	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	31	20	6	2
Bottles_id	1-4	5-8	9-12	13-16
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na	na
Comments (e.g. water smell)	na	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hq incubation	no	no	no	no
Júlias Hq parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THq, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	no	no	no	no
Terasas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes	yes

Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	yes	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	yes	yes
Categories for Carina			DCM	surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

Station SWE25_21

Project	SWE25
Date	250706
Station_id	SWE25_21
Station_coordinates	58°54.6013' N, 10°55.5528' E
Weather	Sunny
Water depth	about 30 m
Arrival time	?

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3
Cast_id	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	28	20	6
Bottles_id	28	20	6
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	no	no	no
Terasas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes
Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	yes

Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	yes
Categories for Carina			DCM

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

Station SWE25_23

Project	SWE25
Date	250707
Station_id	SWE25_23
Station_coordinates	58°49.8122' N, 10°56.9454' E
Weather	cloudy
Water depth	About 50 m
Arrival time	?

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3
Cast_id	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	1-4	5-8	9-12
Bottles_id	48	20	6

CTD Conductivity	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	yes	no	no
Teresas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes
Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	yes
Categories for Carina			DCM

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

Station SWE25_25

Project	SWE25
Date	250707
Station_id	SWE25_25
Station_coordinates	?
Weather	cloudy
Water depth	49 m
Arrival time	?

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3
Cast_id	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	44	18	6
Bottles_id	1-4	5-8	9-12
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	yes	no	no
Terasas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes

Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	yes
Categories for Carina			surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

Station SWE25_27

Project	SWE25
Date	250707
Station_id	SWE25_27
Station_coordinates	58°30.9201' N, 10°59.8837' E
Weather	?
Water depth	58 m
Arrival time	?

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4
Cast_id	1	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	58	40	20	6
Bottles_id	1-4	5-8	9-12	13-16
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	yes	no	no	yes
Terasas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes	yes

Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	yes	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	yes	yes
Categories for Carina			DCM	surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

Station SWE25_28

Project	SWE25
Date	250707
Station_id	SWE25_28
Station_coordinates	58°26.9625' N, 10°59.9232' E
Weather	?
Water depth	?
Arrival time	?

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4
Cast_id	1	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	59	40	10	6
Bottles_id	1-4	5-8	9-12	13-16
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	yes	no	no	yes
Terasas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes	yes

Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	yes	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	yes	yes
Categories for Carina			DCM	surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

Station SWE25_29

Project	SWE25
Date	250707
Station_id	SWE25_29
Station_coordinates	58°21.1993' N, 10°59.8138' E
Weather	?
Water depth	?
Arrival time	?

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4
Cast_id	1	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	82	50	25	6
Bottles_id	1-4	5-8	9-12	13-16
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na	na
CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	yes	no	no	yes
Terasas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes	yes

Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	yes	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	yes	yes
Categories for Carina			DCM	surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

Station SWE25_30

Project	SWE25
Date	250707
Station_id	SWE25_30
Station_coordinates	58°14.8023' N, 11°4.3722' E
Weather	?
Water depth	?
Arrival time	?

Water sampling

Depth_id	1	2	3	4
Cast_id	1	1	1	1
Water depth (m)	94	60	24	6
Bottles_id	1-4	5-8	9-12	13-16
CTD Conductivity	na	na	na	na

CTD Temp (°C)	na	na	na	na
CTD O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
CTD fluorescence	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 (µM)	na	na	na	na
STOX O2 sampling time	na	na	na	na
US H2S (µM)	na	na	na	na
H2S sampling time	na	na	na	na
Water color	na	na	na	na
Comments (e.g, water smell)	na	na	na	na
Tobias GHG DIC	yes	yes	yes	yes
Júlias Hg incubation	no	no	no	no
Júlias Hg parameters (MeHg, MMHg, THg, TOC, AVS, Fe, CDOM-FDOM)	no	no	no	no
Meifangs DNA-RNA samples	no	no	no	no
Courtneys viral analysis	no	no	no	no
Jeffs DOM mass spec	no	no	no	no
Stefans single cell and pathogen	yes	no	no	yes
Teresas N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE	N,TE
Carinas amplicon	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas MG	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas POM, pigments	no	no	yes	yes
Carinas Flow Cytometry	yes	yes	yes	yes
Carinas Actinos	na	na	na	na
Carina Phyto from CTD	no	no	yes	yes
Categories for Carina			DCM	surface

Photo of bottom sediments with CTD

5. Participants

Project	First Name	Last Name	Role
Biox	Eric	Capo	cruise leader
EcoAct/Biox	Carina	Bunse	cruise leader (alternate)
Biox	Meifang	Zhong	water sampling
Biox	Stefan	Bertilsson	water sampling
Biox	Tobia	Politi	water sampling
Biox	Sofia	Paraskevopoulou	water sampling
Biox	Júlia	Dordal Soriano	water sampling
Biox	Isabel	Sanz-Saez	water sampling
Biox	Marta	Royo-Llonch	water sampling
Biox	Elise	Lorre	sediment sampling
Biox	Corentin	Fournier	sediment sampling
Biox	Baraa	Rehamnia	sediment sampling
Biox	Nikolaj	Brask	sediment sampling
Biox	Fangting	He	sediment sampling
Biox	Helena	Filipsson	sediment sampling
Biox	Ursula	Schwarz	sediment sampling
EcoAct	Nicolai	Laufer	water sampling
EcoAct	Teresa	Peil	water sampling
EcoAct	Olga	Kourtchenko	water sampling
EcoAct	Eva	Foth	water sampling

6. Post-expedition analysis for shared data

- Metadata compiled in a Data Management Plan and shared with all
- Metabarcoding data produced and analyzed by Bunse lab
- Metagenomics data produced primarily by Capo lab (Meifang)
- Metatranscriptomics data produced primarily by Stairs lab (Sofia)
- MG/MT will be analyzed by Capolab (Meifang) on Dardel and shared with others.
- Single cell sequencing (but targeted) produced and analyzed by Bertilsson lab.
- Organise a Mini-conference 9 months after the cruise.
- Nutrients will be analyzed with autoanalyzer (Kristineberg)
- Phytoplankton will be analyzed by Bunse lab
- GeoX and 210Pb samples brought to Umeå, GeoX done with EMG equipment, 210Pb datation outsourced
- C14 samples brought to Lund, outsourced
- sedDNA samples brought to Umeå, analyzed in Capo lab

7. Data Sharing statement

- Water column metadata from the 5 fjords: This data will be shared with all participating researchers using a shared folder including a metadata excel file. This includes CTD (conductivity, temperature, depth, salinity, oxygen, pH, fluorescence, chlorophyll), STOX sensor (oxygen), H₂S sensor (H₂S, temperature), AVS (H₂S), nutrients, TDN, TOC.
- Water column sequencing data from the 5 fjords: Sequencing data generated from this project for the water columns of the 5 fjord sites will be shared with the four following PIs (Eric Capo, Carina Bunse, Courtney Stairs, Stefan Bertilsson). This data includes DNA amplicon sequencing from 0.2 um filters (paid by Bunse), from the 3 um and 0.2 um fractions metagenomic (paid by Capo/Bertilsson, metatranscriptomic (paid by Stairs/Capo) and concentrated water samples for viral genomics, and from unfiltered water single-cell genomic data (paid by Bertilsson). Members are welcome to use the data for their own independent research questions, provided that these do not significantly overlap with the main project aims or the research topics of other collaborators: Bertilsson (pathogens *Vibrio*, methane oxidizers), Bunse (ecology of actinomycetes, microbial biodiversity and connectivity of microbial communities between fjords), Capo (anoxygenic anaerobic phototrophs, prokaryotic anaerobic metabolisms, mercury cycling) and Stairs (protists, virus). If data produced and paid by another PI is used, they will be kindly invited as co-authors of the resulting papers but co-authorship requires significant contribution. Before beginning any analyses, members are encouraged to communicate their intended research focus to the group to maintain transparency and prevent conflicts. If other participants of the cruise would like to use it.
- Sediment metadata from the 5 fjords: This data will be shared with all participating researchers. This includes 210Pb dating, geochemistry data (XRF) and 14C dating from Gemax or the gravity core. SedDNA data will be made available for research topics not overlapping with Capo lab research (anoxygenic anaerobic phototrophs, prokaryotic anaerobic metabolisms, mercury cycling).
- Data from the EcoAct and the Biox connecting stations will be obtained and used for projects led by Carina Bunse group.

8. Data Management Plan

The following procedure has been chosen for labelling samples

For water samples Cruise_Station_Cast_bottle_parameter

example : SWE25_S01_C01_B24_PO4 for phosphate in station 1, 1st CTD cast from bottle 24 (surface). If the sample comes from the water mixed from different bottles, the names of each bottle will be written like 21-24.

For sediment samples: Cruise_Station_Corer/cast/core_Seddepth_Parameter

Example: SWE25_S01_GX01A_0-1cm_XRF for XRF samples in station 1, using a gemax corer, first cast, core A (there are two cores caught for every cast). For gravity corer, we could also give letter to the subsections 1 m core: A for 0-1 m, B to 1-2 m until F to the bottom Then the sediment subsampled is a 0-1 cm. GX for Gemax corer, GC for Gravity corer, BC for Box corer

In progress there -> <https://dsw.scilifelab.se/?originalUrl=%2Fdashboard>

11. Expected Outcomes of the joint research cruise from both projects

Expected minimal publication outcomes

- Bertilsson et al : Waterborne pathogens in fjord systems
- Björn et al : Factors controlling methylmercury formation across pelagic redoxclines
- Bonaglia et al : Methane and nitrous oxide distribution in Swedish fjords
- Bunse et al : Connectivity and ecophysiology of microbial communities between fjords
- Capo et al : Microbial ecology in pelagic redoxclines from fjord systems
- Filipsson et al : Morphological adaptations in low oxygen environments- a μ CT approach
- Hawkes et al : Unravelling carbon fluxes in fjords using sample fractionation and carbon isotope analysis
- Nascimento et al : Uncovering the potential resources for the recolonization of aquatic ecosystems by micrometazoans when oxygen conditions improve.
- Stairs et al : Protist:prokaryotic interaction in oxygen-deficient waters
- Bunse et al: Actinomycetota ecology in coastal environments
- Bunse et al: Ecophysiology and microbial diversity of Nordic marine communities
- Bunse et al: Impact of DOM and trace elements on interactions between marine microbial community members

Other expected outcomes/products

The launch of a working group of Swedish researchers to study coastal systems with a holistic approach i.e. biogeochemical data and microbial ecology data from water columns, surface sediments and long sediment cores. This working group will be linked to AMRI, a Swedish network of aquatic microbial ecologists.

The creation of an interactive tool that will be used by scientists or for outreach activities to explore biogeochemical and microbial ecology data obtained from coastal systems with low-oxygen water columns (including the Baltic Sea). This will be done locally with Scandinavia first and then scaled up to the planet. We will be inspired from ongoing initiatives such as EMBL TREC data hub and the Ocean Data Platform.